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Mindfulness and Its Demographic and Behavioral Correlates Among University Students in Pakistan: A Cross-Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background

Mindfulness is increasingly recognized as a critical factor in student well-being and academic performance, yet its demographic and behavioral correlates remain underexplored in South Asian contexts.

Objective

To examine levels of mindfulness and identify key demographic and behavioral predictors among university students in Pakistan.

Methods

A cross-sectional survey was administered to 344 university students aged 18-28 years. The Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS) was used to assess mindfulness. Demographic and behavioral data were collected via structured questionnaire. Reliability was assessed using Cronbach's alpha. K-means cluster analysis identified mindfulness profiles. Associations between clusters and demographic variables were examined using chi-square and ANOVA. Multiple regression determined predictors of mindfulness scores.

Results

The MAAS demonstrated excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = .894$). Cluster analysis identified three distinct mindfulness groups: low (32.8%), medium (47.4%), and high (19.8%). Females were significantly overrepresented in the low mindfulness cluster ($p < .001$). Social media use and academic year were also associated with mindfulness levels. Regression analysis indicated gender as the sole significant predictor, with females scoring lower than males ($\beta = -.188, p = .001$). No significant associations were observed for age or socioeconomic status.

Conclusion

Pakistani university students display considerable variability in mindfulness, with gender and social media use emerging as salient correlates. These findings highlight the need for tailored mindfulness interventions, particularly for female students and frequent social media users, to foster student well-being in higher education settings.

Introduction

Mindfulness, defined as the self-regulation of attention toward present-moment experiences with an attitude of openness and non-judgment (1), has gained substantial empirical support as a protective factor for mental health, academic achievement, and overall well-being (2) (3) (4). Among university students a group frequently exposed to intense academic, social, and developmental challenges the cultivation of mindfulness is associated with reduced stress, improved cognitive performance, and enhanced emotional regulation (5) (6).

Despite the growing global emphasis on mindfulness in higher education, much of the extant literature originates from Western contexts. These findings may not fully capture the unique sociocultural, familial, and behavioral dynamics present in South Asian countries such as Pakistan, where collectivist values, extended family structures, and rapidly changing digital habits shape student experiences in distinct ways. Research on mindfulness among Pakistani university students remains limited, with few studies systematically investigating its demographic and behavioral determinants.

Emerging evidence suggests that mindfulness may be influenced by factors such as gender, socioeconomic status, and technology use (7) (8). Gender disparities in mindfulness have been inconsistently reported, with some studies indicating lower mindfulness among females, potentially due to heightened rumination or differential stress exposures (9). Socioeconomic context, academic pressures, and family background may also impact students' capacity for present-moment awareness (10). Of growing relevance is the pervasive use of social media among young adults, which has been associated with reduced attention, increased mind-wandering, and lower mindfulness scores (8) (11). Given the paucity of research in Pakistan and the potential impact of cultural, academic, and technological factors, the present study aims to address three key objectives:

1. To assess mindfulness levels among Pakistani university students using the Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS).
2. To identify distinct mindfulness profiles using cluster analysis.
3. To examine demographic and behavioral predictors of mindfulness, with a focus on gender, academic year, socioeconomic status, and social media usage.

Methods

Study Design and Setting

A cross-sectional quantitative study was conducted to examine mindfulness and its demographic and behavioral correlates among university students in Pakistan. Data collection occurred between 2025, utilizing both online and in-person recruitment.

Participants

Eligibility criteria included: 1. Current enrollment as an undergraduate or graduate student at a recognized Pakistani university, 2. age between 18 and 28 years, and 3. ability to provide informed consent. A total of 344 students participated in the study.

Measures

Demographic and Behavioral Data

A structured questionnaire was developed to collect data on age, gender, academic year, family type, marital status, socioeconomic status (based on self-reported monthly pocket money and family income), accommodation, employment status, parental education and occupation, geographical background, chronic health conditions, smoking status, study preferences, extracurricular activity participation, daily phone and social media usage, and overall physical activity level.

Mindfulness

Mindfulness was assessed using the **Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS)** (Brown & Ryan, 2003). The MAAS is a 15-item, self-report instrument designed to measure a core characteristic of dispositional mindfulness,

namely, open or receptive awareness of and attention to what is taking place in the present. Items are rated on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = Almost always; 6 = Almost never), with higher scores indicating greater mindfulness. In the current sample, the MAAS demonstrated excellent internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = .894$).

Procedure

After obtaining approval from the Superior University Institutional Review Board (IRB), data collection was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Participants provided informed consent prior to participation. The survey was distributed electronically via Google Forms (for online participants) and as paper forms in classrooms (for in-person participants). Data were anonymized and securely stored.

Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 26. Descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages) summarized participant characteristics and key study variables.

- **Reliability Analysis:** Internal consistency of the MAAS was assessed using Cronbach's alpha.
- **Cluster Analysis:** K-means cluster analysis was performed on MAAS total scores to identify distinct mindfulness profiles.
- **Group Comparisons:** Chi-square tests were used to examine associations between mindfulness clusters and categorical demographic/behavioral variables. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) assessed differences in age across clusters.
- **Regression Analysis:** Multiple linear regression was conducted to identify demographic and behavioral predictors of mindfulness (MAAS total score), with gender, academic year, socioeconomic status, and social media frequency entered as independent variables.
- **Statistical Significance:** A two-tailed p-value $< .05$ was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results

Sample Characteristics

The final analyzed sample consisted of **344 participants** (117 males, 34.0%; 227 females, 66.0%) aged between 18 to 28 years ($M = 21.76$, $SD = 1.83$). Participants were predominantly Pakistani nationals (97.4%), single (96.2%), and middle-income socioeconomic status (70.3%). A majority of participants (79.1%) reported using social media several times daily, and most preferred studying alone (70.6%). Further demographic details are provided in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Sample Demographic Characteristics ($N = 344$)

Demographic and Key Variables ($N = 344$)

Variable	Response Option	Frequency (%)
Gender	Male	117 (34.0%)
	Female	227 (66.0%)
Family Type	Joint Family	119 (34.6%)
	Nuclear Family	225 (65.4%)
Parental Status of Marriage	Married	337 (98.0%)
	Divorced	1 (0.3%)
	Separated	6 (1.7%)
Nationality	Pakistani	335 (97.4%)
	Overseas	9 (2.6%)
Academic Year	1	62 (18.0%)
	2	66 (19.2%)
	3	66 (19.2%)
	4	78 (22.7%)
	5	72 (20.9%)

Marital Status	Married	12 (3.5%)
	Single	331 (96.2%)
	Divorced	1 (0.3%)
Type of Accommodation	Hostel	180 (52.3%)
	Home	164 (47.7%)
Employment Status	Employed	28 (8.1%)
	Unemployed	316 (91.9%)
Socioeconomic Status	Low-income	13 (3.8%)
	Middle-income	242 (70.3%)
	High-income	89 (25.9%)
Geographical Background	Urban area	250 (72.7%)
	Sub-urban area	54 (15.7%)
	Rural area	40 (11.6%)
Monthly Pocket Money (PKR)	<15,000	85 (24.7%)
	16,000-30,000	116 (33.7%)
	31,000-45,000	82 (23.8%)
	46,000-60,000	29 (8.4%)
	>60,000	32 (9.3%)
Chronic Health Conditions	Yes	38 (11.0%)
	No	306 (89.0%)
Smoking	Never smoked	314 (91.3%)
	Ex-smoker	12 (3.5%)
	Current smoker	18 (5.2%)
Mother's Education Level	PhD	19 (5.5%)
	University Degree	71 (20.6%)
	Master's Degree	86 (25.0%)
	Secondary School	79 (23.0%)
	Diploma	29 (8.4%)
	No formal education	60 (17.4%)
Mother's Occupation	Management / Business	30 (8.7%)
	Professional (Doctor, Lawyer, Engineer)	36 (10.5%)
	Technical/Skilled Trade	6 (1.7%)
	Sales	2 (0.6%)
	Education	28 (8.1%)
	Unemployed/Not working	2 (0.6%)
	Retired	7 (2.0%)
	Housewife	233 (67.7%)
Father's Education Level	PhD	25 (7.3%)
	University Degree	82 (23.8%)
	Master's Degree	103 (29.9%)
	Secondary School	78 (22.7%)
	Diploma	22 (6.4%)
	No formal education	34 (9.9%)
Father's Occupation	Management / Business	221 (64.2%)
	Professional (Doctor, Lawyer, Engineer)	78 (22.7%)
	Technical/Skilled Trade	1 (0.3%)

	Service Industry	7 (2.0%)
	Sales	2 (0.6%)
	Education	16 (4.7%)
	Unemployed/Not working	3 (0.9%)
	Retired	6 (1.7%)
	House Husband	7 (2.0%)
Transportation to School	Walk	115 (33.4%)
	Bicycle	5 (1.5%)
	Public transportation	50 (14.5%)
	Personal vehicle	150 (43.6%)
	Carpool	24 (7.0%)
Extracurricular Activities	Yes	200 (58.1%)
	No	144 (41.9%)
Study Preference	Alone	243 (70.6%)
	In a group	94 (27.3%)
	With a tutor	7 (2.0%)
Social Media Usage	Several times a day	272 (79.1%)
	Once a day	50 (14.5%)
	A few times a week	15 (4.4%)
	Rarely	7 (2.0%)
Overall Activity Level	Very active	49 (14.2%)
	Moderately active	202 (58.7%)
	Lightly active	78 (22.7%)
	Sedentary	15 (4.4%)
Control Over Kids in Home	Mother	150 (43.6%)
	Father	160 (46.5%)
	Both	34 (9.9%)
Phone Usage per Day	Less than 1 hour	19 (5.5%)
	1-3 hours	87 (25.3%)
	3-5 hours	103 (29.9%)
	5-7 hours	78 (22.7%)
	More than 7 hours	57 (16.6%)

Reliability Analysis

Cronbach's alpha was computed to examine the internal consistency of the 15-item Mindful Attention Awareness Scale (MAAS). Results indicated excellent reliability ($\alpha = .894$), confirming strong internal consistency among items. Item-total correlations indicated no problematic items (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Reliability of the MAAS (Cronbach's Alpha)

Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Alpha Range if Item Deleted
15	.894	.883-.893

MAAS Scale Response Percentages

Participants' responses to MAAS items reflected a range of mindfulness-related experiences (Table 3). Items indicating lapses in present-moment awareness and automatic or inattentive behaviors were commonly endorsed, though the most frequently endorsed item pertained to delayed emotional awareness.

Table 3: MAAS Scale Item Response Percentages (N = 344)

Questions	Almost always	Very frequently	Somewhat frequently	Somewhat infrequently	Very infrequently	Almost never
I could be experiencing some emotion and not be conscious of it until some time later.	47 (13.7%)	43 (12.5%)	130 (37.8%)	65 (18.9%)	32 (9.3%)	27 (7.8%)
I break or spill things because of carelessness, not paying attention, or thinking of something else.	13 (3.8%)	53 (15.4%)	102 (29.7%)	73 (21.2%)	56 (16.3%)	47 (13.7%)
I find it difficult to stay focused on what's happening in the present.	17 (4.9%)	54 (15.7%)	120 (34.9%)	70 (20.3%)	49 (14.2%)	34 (9.9%)
I tend to walk quickly to get where I'm going without paying attention to what I experience along the way.	22 (6.4%)	54 (15.7%)	112 (32.6%)	77 (22.4%)	51 (14.8%)	28 (8.1%)
I tend not to notice feelings of physical tension or discomfort until they really grab my attention.	22 (6.4%)	53 (15.4%)	111 (32.3%)	94 (27.3%)	35 (10.2%)	29 (8.4%)
I forget a person's name almost as soon as I've been told it for the first time.	19 (5.5%)	51 (14.8%)	92 (26.7%)	92 (26.7%)	39 (11.3%)	51 (14.8%)
It seems I am "running on automatic," without much awareness of what I'm doing.	17 (4.9%)	38 (11.0%)	97 (28.2%)	91 (26.5%)	54 (15.7%)	47 (13.7%)
I rush through activities without being really attentive to them.	12 (3.5%)	35 (10.2%)	101 (29.4%)	85 (24.7%)	64 (18.6%)	47 (13.7%)
I get so focused on the goal I want to	16 (4.7%)	42 (12.2%)	107 (31.1%)	97 (28.2%)	41 (11.9%)	41 (11.9%)

achieve that I lose touch with what I'm doing right now to get there.						
I do jobs or tasks automatically, without being aware of what I'm doing.	14 (4.1%)	40 (11.6%)	74 (21.5%)	89 (25.9%)	62 (18.0%)	65 (18.9%)
I find myself listening to someone with one ear, doing something else at the same time.	19 (5.5%)	64 (18.6%)	104 (30.2%)	83 (24.1%)	33 (9.6%)	41 (11.9%)
I drive places on 'automatic pilot' and then wonder why I went there.	16 (4.7%)	40 (11.6%)	75 (21.8%)	85 (24.7%)	53 (15.4%)	75 (21.8%)
I find myself preoccupied with the future or the past.	22 (6.4%)	57 (16.6%)	91 (26.5%)	94 (27.3%)	49 (14.2%)	31 (9.0%)
I find myself doing things without paying attention.	19 (5.5%)	43 (12.5%)	87 (25.3%)	85 (24.7%)	64 (18.6%)	46 (13.4%)
I snack without being aware that I'm eating.	19 (5.5%)	47 (13.7%)	71 (20.6%)	62 (18.0%)	65 (18.9%)	80 (23.3%)

Cluster Analysis

A K-means cluster analysis was performed using MAAS total scores. Three mindfulness clusters were identified: Low mindfulness (n = 113; 32.8%), Medium mindfulness (n = 163; 47.4%), and High mindfulness (n = 68; 19.8%). Mean mindfulness scores differed significantly among clusters (**Table 4**).

Table 4: Cluster Analysis Results

Cluster	N (%)	MAAS Mean Score (SD)
Low Mindfulness	113 (32.8%)	41.84 (5.55)
Medium Mindfulness	163 (47.4%)	55.94 (4.57)
High Mindfulness	68 (19.8%)	75.50 (7.12)

Demographic Differences Between Mindfulness Clusters

Chi-square analyses explored demographic differences among mindfulness clusters. Significant associations were found for gender ($\chi^2(2) = 15.92, p < .001$), academic year ($\chi^2(8) = 17.56, p = .025$), and frequency of social media use ($\chi^2(6) = 13.98, p = .030$). Females were more prevalent in the low mindfulness cluster, whereas males were more evenly distributed. No significant relationships emerged with socioeconomic status, marital status, or other demographics (all $p > .05$). (Table 4)

Table 4: Significant Demographic Differences by Mindfulness Cluster

Demographic Variable	χ^2	df	p-value
Gender	15.92	2	< .001***
Academic Year	17.56	8	.025*
Social Media Use	13.98	6	.030*

* $p < .05$, ** $p < .001$

Age Differences Across Mindfulness Clusters

A one-way ANOVA tested age differences among the three mindfulness clusters. No significant differences were observed: Low mindfulness (M = 21.63, SD = 1.83), Medium mindfulness (M = 21.88, SD = 1.87), and High mindfulness (M = 21.66, SD = 1.81), $F(2, 341) = 0.756$, $p = .470$ (Table 5). Post hoc analyses (Tukey's) also confirmed no significant group differences.

Table 5: One-Way ANOVA for Age by Mindfulness Cluster

Cluster	N	Mean Age (SD)
Low Mindfulness	113	21.63 (1.83)
Medium Mindfulness	163	21.88 (1.87)
High Mindfulness	68	21.66 (1.81)

Predictors of Mindfulness Scores: Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression was conducted with mindfulness (MAAS total score) as the dependent variable, and gender, academic year, socioeconomic status, and social media frequency as independent variables. The regression model was statistically significant but accounted for only a small proportion of variance in mindfulness scores ($R^2 = .042$, Adjusted $R^2 = .031$, $F(4, 339) = 3.71$, $p = .006$). Gender significantly predicted mindfulness ($\beta = -.188$, $p = .001$), with females scoring approximately 5 points lower on average compared to males. Other predictors were not statistically significant (Table 6).

Table 6: Regression Analysis Predicting Mindfulness Scores

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p-value
Gender	-5.16	1.47	-.188	-3.51	.001**
Academic Year	0.33	0.50	.036	0.67	.504
Socioeconomic Status	0.17	1.41	.006	0.12	.904
Frequency of Social Media	-1.30	1.08	-.065	-1.21	.228

Model: $F(4, 339) = 3.71$, $p = .006$, $R^2 = .042$, Adjusted $R^2 = .031$

** $p < .01$

Summary of Findings

The mindfulness scale demonstrated high reliability. Cluster analysis revealed three distinct mindfulness groups differing significantly by gender, academic year, and social media use, but not by age. Regression analysis showed gender as a significant predictor, with females consistently reporting lower mindfulness. Other demographic factors did not significantly predict mindfulness scores.

Discussion

This study provides new insights into the levels and correlates of mindfulness among university students in Pakistan, using a sample and validated psychometric approach. Three main findings emerge: 1. Significant variability in mindfulness, with nearly one-third of students demonstrating low mindfulness; 2. Gender and social media use as salient correlates, with females and frequent social media users reporting lower mindfulness; and 3. Limited predictive value of age and socioeconomic status in this context. The overall moderate levels of mindfulness observed align with recent findings in university populations globally (12). Notably, our study found that females were significantly overrepresented in the low mindfulness cluster, a trend reported in both Western and Asian samples. For instance, (13) found similar gender differences among Chinese university students, linking lower mindfulness in females to higher stress and rumination. These results highlight the potential benefit of gender-sensitive mindfulness interventions in university settings. Frequent social media use was associated with lower mindfulness, consistent with the growing literature on digital distractions and attentional depletion among young adults (14). Recent evidence suggests that high engagement with social media platforms may exacerbate mind-wandering, reduce present-moment awareness, and contribute to poorer psychological outcomes (15). Our findings underscore the importance of digital wellness programs and mindful technology use within higher education. The association between academic year and mindfulness, though statistically significant, did not show a consistent pattern, echoing results from recent multicenter studies indicating that academic stressors and adaptation may fluctuate across university years (16). In contrast to some earlier reports, neither age nor socioeconomic status predicted mindfulness, possibly due to the homogeneity of our sample or cultural factors buffering against these influences. Given the robust link between mindfulness and student well-being, these findings support the integration of mindfulness-based programs into university curricula, with an emphasis on supporting female students and those with high social media engagement. Recent intervention studies have demonstrated that even brief mindfulness training can improve attention, emotion regulation, and reduce digital dependency among university students (17).

Limitations

This study is subject to several limitations. The cross-sectional design precludes causal inferences. Self-reported data may be affected by social desirability bias. The study focused on students from Pakistani universities, which may limit generalizability to other cultural or age groups. Future research should employ longitudinal or experimental designs and incorporate objective behavioral measures.

Conclusion

In summary, this study advances understanding of mindfulness and its demographic and behavioral correlates in Pakistani university students. The results highlight the need for gender-sensitive and digitally mindful interventions to enhance student well-being and academic performance in the digital era.

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